

CREATING A DATASET FOR KEYPHRASE EXTRACTION IN PHYSICS PUBLICATIONS AND PATENTS

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Abstract

Extracting keyphrases and entities can be an important first step in many Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Information Retrieval (IR) Tasks. There are many datasets to train models for standard entities, but it is hard to find data that can be used for more domain specific applications. The types of keyphrases someone wants to extract vary enormously between different fields, which makes otherwise successful algorithms perform poorly on them. One of the fields where this is the case is Physics, specifically to process physics publications and patents. In comparison to news articles or social media, the typical entities like Organization, Location or Person are not helpful when extracting important information from publications or patents. There are few dataset annotations for specific domains, and even when they exist they are not easily transferable. This work contributes an annotated dataset for the facilitation of information retrieval and extraction in Physics. The dataset spans Physics Patents as well as Publications. It covers both of these document types to enable future work between them. This can facilitate future work such as tracking inventions from the first emergence in a publication to the adaption in a patent.

Keywords: Keyphrase Extraction, Named Entity Recognition, Dataset, Semantic Search, Physics, Patents, Publications

INTRODUCTION

Extracting keyphrases and named entities is one of the fundamental tasks of semantic search based on knowledge graphs. Those tasks can be crucial for retrieving the most relevant body of work, but it can also help in analysing the developments in research over time, recommend citations or search for a combination of keyphrases.

As more papers and patents get published every year, it takes a lot of effort to keep up with the current state-of-the-art in a lot of fields. Retrieval systems only address this to an extent as it is hard to search for certain methods or even combinations of entities, in particular for a specified domain such as physics. Especially patents are hard to retrieve because of the fact that certain descriptions are very close to legal language [1]. For some types of data and specific types of entities this task is practically solved, but the extraction of keyphrases is a harder task than just identifying entities. Extracting and classifying keyphrases and entities also helps with the creation of knowledge graphs and the population of existing ones. Considering the relationships

between the different parts of a query helps to improve the retrieval accuracy.

Most of the research on Keyphrase Extraction and Named Entity Recognition (NER) takes place on a few datasets, and application to more general data can be disappointing. NER datasets are usually restricted to a few key entities such as Person, Organization and Location. In addition, there is Fine-Grained Named Entity Recognition [2] that differentiates between types of those three entities and adds a few more categories. The more general categories help with the retrieval when it comes to every day topics, but fail when it comes to something really domain specific. There have been shared tasks sometimes to improve the state of NER and keyphrase extraction, that try to improve the state of the problem, but they usually limited in scope and what they cover. Two applications of this that we are particular interested in are building a knowledge graph for semantic search and searching for entity combinations, which can be build on top of the open search index or linked to other search engines (Example: Materials in semiconductors that can change over time as more research and development takes place).

Even if a scientific publication is in the same domain as the patent, the language can be very different, which makes it difficult to apply existing algorithms to a patent corpus for retrieval [1]. This work is probably closest to the shared task of SemEval 2017 [3] that proposed a task with a dataset that covered the keyphrases of process, material and task for the fields of Computer Science, Material Science and Physics. We use the types Process, Material and Task that are used in this dataset but also add some more entities that fit the domains of Physics in Patents and Publications well. With this work we want to build a bridge between Publications and Patents and we envision work that can use this to its advantage. All of the annotated documents that are used to create this dataset are freely available, either from the patent offices or from arxiv. Those resources are linked together with the dataset.

Our main contribution is a new annotated dataset. In addition, we provide reasonable baselines and models for all of the tasks to enable future comparisons and improvements on those baselines. Those first results are provided by a neural network based model we trained on the data, and therefore provide a good starting point for future research with room for improvements. The task is generally harder than NER which is reflected in those baselines. Similar observations have been made in the past for similar tasks. Keyphrase extraction is generally a harder problem than NER because they can vary significantly between domains,

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and the extracted keyphrases can be longer than typical NER tags [3]. The paper is structured in the following way: The next section describes the related work and the background to the task including the most important datasets that have been created in the field. Section Collecting the Corpus describes how the patents and publication for the annotation were selected. Section Annotation Process describes how the dataset was created and annotations were collected. Section Dataset Overview gives an overview over the dataset and Baseline Results creates simple baselines for the dataset future work can be compared against. The paper concludes with Section Conclusion and describes potential future work in Section .

BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

Notably, there have been a few common datasets that are generally used as a test for new named entity recognition. There are also a few domain specific datasets, but there is very little in the domain of physics Some of them are either not openly available, use only a limited to the three most common entities.

Background

NER and keyphrase extractions are fairly well explored field when it comes to news articles and content of every day life (such as social media), but there are a lot of domain specific keyphrases where almost no datasets exist. News articles are a fairly broad as they can talk about a lot of different domains, but the topics are more general than a very specific scientific domain such as physics. In those cases, the state-of-the-art approaches for those fields don't fall short, but they encounter tasks that they were not trained for.

The second most common annotations after news articles can be found in the domain of medicine. A lot of annotations for different molecules, diseases or pharmaceuticals exist. Other domains do have very little annotation in comparison.

An advantage of the news based annotations with the entity types of Person, Location, Corporation is that other extracted keyphrases from the text that don't fall into those categories can be linked to existing knowledge bases such as dbpedia, a knowledge base based on wikipedia [4]. This knowledge base contains fairly general knowledge, making it a good target to link to from news articles. An ontology extracted keyphrases and entities of this dataset could be linked against is the ScienceWise Ontology [5]. Some other promising Ontology projects exist in scientific domains, such as Biology and even Math.

Related Work

One of the most popular tasks or dataset is the CoNLL-2003 Shared Task [6]. This task has a huge body of resource associated with it and the state-of-the-art has been beaten many times. The main types in this dataset are Location, Organization and Person. This makes this task very interesting

for specific applications such as tagging news articles, but is not helpful as a source for training in many other domains such as our target domain of physics.

Another dataset that is frequently used as a testbed is the english part of Ontonotes5 [7]. Beside other annotation, Ontonotes provides more entity types such as Person, Organization, Location, Work Of Art, GPE and others. Along with those eleven entity types, it also provides annotations for different measurable types of quantities. As some of the entity types in this task are less specific, the task is closer to the one in this work, but still doesn't include most of the keyphrases that would be useful to build a physics based knowledge graph.

The WNUT2017 shared task [8] is yet another task that comes with a dataset of annotated entity classes. Entity classes it provides are Person, Location, Corporation, Consumer Good, Creative Work and Group. The goal of this task was to solve emergent entities in the domains of social media or news. Emergent entities are newly emerged entities previously not seen that might cause problems to NER models. We envision the usage of the dataset in a similar way, where it would enable models to be trained that can identify newly emergent technologies in the physics domain.

The task that includes the dataset that is the closest to this work is the SemEval 2017 task [3]. The SemEval task was constructed out of three different tasks, where one dealt with the extraction and classification of keyphrases and entities.

In addition to this, there are several dataset for different scientific domains, such as the NCBI Disease Dataset [9], the i2b2/UTHealth shared task [10] or astronomy [11].

COLLECTING THE CORPUS

The corpus for annotation was collected from arxiv¹ and freely available patents from the USPTO². We extracted 32,832 documents in a pre-selection stage.

Patents

A seed of patents was selected from the computing related patent class in physics (G06). We extended to the most semantically similar patent classes. This selection was based on previous analysis on which patent classes were connected with each other [1]. A selection this way has the advantage that we do not just use a single class, but a bigger subset of the big field of physics. We sourced patents that were created from 2010 to 2018 and created document embeddings for the claims sections with the gensim toolkit [12]. The following hyper-parameters were used in creating the embeddings:

- algorithm: skip-gram
- iterations: 50
- window size: 7

¹ https://arxiv.org/help/bulk_data

² <https://developer.uspto.gov/data>

- dimensions: 300
- min count: 10
- sub-sampling threshold: 10^{-5}
- negative sample: 5

We have chosen the claims section as it generally is one of the best sections for information retrieval and the most important section when it comes to prior art search [13]. We sourced patents that were not too similar to each other because we wanted to avoid overlaps between patents that are very similar to each other to have a broader selection of tokens. The similarity was measured with euclidean distance and we maximized the distance between the pre-selection documents. Unlike this approach, it would also be reasonable to select patents that are similar to each other as it could highlight the evolution in certain topics.

Publications

Next we collected physics publications from arxiv between the years 2010 and 2018. Similar to the physics patents, we also created document embeddings for the publications with the same parameters as we used for the patents. For this selection, we identified pairs of patent and publication that were close to each other. The selection was made this way to enable future work to draw parallels between the two sources that use very different language.

A total of 1000 initial documents were sourced this way for annotation, although not all of them were used in the end as the annotators didn't get to them. We included author and organization descriptions whenever possible from different sections of the documents, because they are rarer in full texts of publications and patents compared to other sources.

ANNOTATION PROCESS

The dataset is designed for the tasks of mention level keyphrase identification and classification. We use the following keyphrase types:

- ORGANIZATION (Any organizational form, can be institution, agency, department)
- PROCESS (Methods used in creating the product, e.g. execution of instructions; oxidization)
- MATERIAL (Physical materials or any tangible elements used. Example: hydrogen, water, catalyst)
- TASK (The problem or task at hand to solve: Named Entity Recognition, Information Extraction)
- PART (Parts used in creating the final product or parts of a whole. Example: touch sensor, graphical user interface)

The annotation process was done in two steps: Pre-annotation and manual annotation. We decided to split the annotation in those two steps to conserve the time of our volunteers, which led to us being able to collect more annotations.

Automatic Pre-annotation

We selected the keyphrase types because it is a good mixture between classical named entity recognition and more challenging keyphrase like types. We automatically pre-annotated the data wherever possible, because solely manual annotation of keyphrases would be very time consuming. Domain specific annotations for our selected types are more complicated to spot and identify for manual annotators than Organization or Person. To support this, we used a pre-trained bert based NER model [14] that was fine-tuned on the CoNLL dataset [6] to do a first pre-annotation. Afterwards we transfer the model and fine-tune it to the SemEval dataset. The main one that was missing was the PART tag. The main disadvantage of this approach was that longer keyphrases were not identified in a lot of cases. Nevertheless the approach facilitated the annotation process as many of the simpler keyphrases and entities were correctly tagged.

Manual Annotation

For the manual annotation, we recruited five volunteers. All of the volunteers are experts in the field of physics and are employed in different capacities at CERN. We prepared sample annotations from the pre-annotated corpus that fulfilled our quality assessments and showed those example annotations to the annotators. We instructed the annotators to also correct pre-annotated keyphrases when they thought the models from the pre-annotation step made an error. In addition, we provided the annotators with guidelines to help them getting introduced to the task. As the annotators are all experts in their field, we opted to double annotate the documents. When there was a disagreement between the annotations, a manual check was performed by a third expert. The agreement between the annotators was measured with the average cohen's kappa and fleiss coefficients, which are respectively 0.81 and 0.82.

Documents were annotated with the doccano open source annotation tool [15], which allows each user to have their own user space. The tool was publicly hosted and all annotators had access to it over two months.

OVERVIEW OVER THE ANNOTATIONS

This section gives a brief description of the annotated dataset and its characteristics. The annotated dataset is split into a training and validation set. The training data set contains a total of 300 annotated documents, with even splits between Publications and Patents. The test dataset contains 100 annotated datasets with an equal split as well. While

Table 1: Overview over the dataset.

Domains	Physics Pubs and Patents
Classes	Org, Process, Mat, Task, Part
Training Documents	300
Training Publications	150
Training Patents	150
Validation Documents	100
Validation Publications	50
Validation Patents	50
Number of Keyphrases	4,642

splitting between the training and testset, there was no consideration for splitting them according to their semantic similarity as we did when selecting the documents from the two fields. This could have been done as well, but we decided against this approach and randomly sampled the table. This still give us a good mix of already seen and unseen keyphrases. Table 1 shows an overview over the dataset statistics. The data for the Publications and Patents texts come in different forms. Publication abstracts are available in textual forms and don't need any further processing to be used for the annotation process. There are the few data types for patents, but the most useful one for this analysis is the xml based. We extract the claims section from the patents. For this dataset we only use patents that where granted by the patent offices.

BASELINE MODEL AND RESULTS

We present a baseline model and results in this section as a way to compare future results against the annotated dataset and to provide an easy way to get started with keyphrase extraction.

Baseline model

We trained a bidirectional LSTM (long short term memory) model with a CRF (Conditional random field) layer on the data. Models similar to this have shown to provide good results on NER tasks in the past. One of the other advantages of this approach is that compared to other models, we do not have to do careful feature engineering. The bidirectional LSTM layer does a forward and backwards pass over the data to utilize contextual information before and after the tag which can be especially useful for the more complex longer keyphrases. Each word is represented as a vector of character and word embeddings. We used the adam optimizer [16] and trained the model for 20 epochs. Figure 1 shows the general layout of the bidirectional LSTM with all the network layers.

The baseline shows that this task is harder than pure NER tasks. NER task results on CoNLL for example tend to reach F1 scores higher than 90. The baselines is similar

Figure 1: DNN model used to create the baseline. The model and the model layer visualization were created in keras.

Table 2: Baseline evaluation results for the dataset.

Metric	Result
F1	0.33
Precision	0.27
Recall	0.42

to the the results some of the participants in the SemEval task reached, which is plausible as the task also focused on the more complicated field of keyphrase extraction and identification.

Results

For the baselines, standard evaluations metrics are calculated, namely F1-score, precision and recall. Table 2 shows the baseline results for the datasets which can be improved upon by more intricate methods. We provide a baseline for that annotated dataset to have a starting point for future comparisons.

CONCLUSION

Keyphrase Extraction or the extraction of named entities is an important first step in many applications in NER or Information Retrieval. With this work, we introduced a new dataset for keyphrase extraction in the physics domain for publications and patents. In addition, we trained a neural network model for this task. This model provides a baseline future work can be evaluated against. The bi-LSTM model with CRF layer has been chosen because this approach was applied successfully to similar tasks in the past. The sim-

ple baselines are as expected lower than other baseline for NER tasks considering that keyphrase extraction is a harder problem than NER. Similar previous tasks that dealt with keyphrase extraction showed similar results in terms of F1 score, recall and precision. The annotations span publications and patents on purpose to enable work that can track progress between the fields, highlight the differences between the language or make it easier to train models that are successful on patent data.

FUTURE WORK

We plan to improve on the baselines of the dataset and use the result of the extractions to link to different ontologies and knowledge bases. For new emergent nodes that don't exist in the knowledge bases, the knowledge base can be populated with the newly extracted nodes. In addition, we plan to expand the dataset with more annotations in the future. Training the models on more data would further improve the models trained on the dataset. Another interesting direction we would like to explore is to annotate the dataset for semantic relationships extraction. As the concepts are already annotated, this would be less effort than the initial creation of the dataset.

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